

Impact of Change Management in Achieving Objectives in IT Project Management

Marlyn Dodampe Gamage

Cardiff Metropolitan University
Llandaff Campus, Western Avenue, Cardiff, CF5 2YB
marlyndp17@gmail.com

Prabath Samarawickrama Wanniarachchige

PRINCE2® Practitioner | Microsoft® MCT | ERP Consultant
Sri Lanka
prabathSWL@gmail.com

Abstract:

Management of Information Technology projects is a trending topic in Sri Lanka, due to considerable number of project failures that happened during the last decade. Most of the failures happened during the project management process as projects get affected due to various changes. All the processes handled by humans and therefore, errors can be happened, but if project managers can handle the changes in a project with a proper change management process, it will be a concrete reason to get success in an IT project.

The author used the deductive approach for the research and with the help of existing literature, the researcher has identified the factors that affect the change management of IT projects as change of project scope, budget, managers, quality, resource allocation and technology. With those findings, author came up with the conceptual model followed by hypothesis to proceed with primary data gathering using quantitative method. It is based on Colombo District as the population of IT Industry in Sri Lanka is huge. Stratified random sampling technique is used to determine a sample that can gather data with high reliability and accuracy. Survey is limited IT professionals with direct and indirect experience in project management. Experience and good education qualifications are also considered to get a good interpretation on Project Management integrated with change management. Secondary data is extracted from the literature available.

Reliability and validity tests have performed to assess the validity of questionnaire. The Pearson correlation and liner regression have executed to evaluate hypothesis in relation to each independent variable with dependent variable. Analysis of multiple regression is done to assess the impact of all independent variables towards the dependent variable. The results of the study showed that there is a strong relationship between the independent variables towards the dependent variable and the impact is evaluated deeply. Based on that further recommendation are depicted together with contribution to both theory and future studies by filling the gaps in existing literature.

Keywords:

Information Technology; Project Management; Change Management.

1. Introduction

In 1950, the computer was introduced and with Internet the world has become a global village around 1980. Industries have moved to IT solutions in order to gain more efficiency and profit, However, many industries could not succeed in their IT projects with a considerable number of failures in some companies. The most failing rate is suffered by government projects.

In Sri Lanka with highly results skilled workforce the IT industry has flourished drastically, and it is anticipated to reach the revenue goal of 3 billion by the year 2024 [1][2]. The business community in Sri Lanka started to compete with overseas IT companies by providing reliable solutions on the sectors of network, hardware, security and software. Back in the early years, the IT project management was only used in the aerospace industry, the main focus for just to rely on the quantitative methods to control project schedule and the quality of output product [3][4]. With the rapid growth of IT industry, the IT project management has become one of the mainstreams now and a globally accessed process used by organizations to accomplish their goals of Information technology projects. It includes planning, prioritizing of resources and controlling various tasks and activities that are required in project [5][6].

Change management is also an important element in managing the sum of all changes that transpire during the course of a project, and it can take place through using tools and processes [7][10]. The many options that exist for models, structures and degrees of governance make change management a more diffuse discipline than project management [8]. Very different approaches underlie change management and project management. And yet, these two dots are two of the three essentials for success in any change that was deemed necessary for the business – alongside people. The project manager embeds the process of change management in their field of view and action, and a dedicated team is given the resources and involvement needed to manage it. It is the responsibility of the project manager to ensure that team members adhere to the parameters of the project and follow up on the changes in their practices [9].

Still, it is considered by some scholars to require the mastering of several skills for its successful accomplishment, as is the case for the hierarchical arenas of change management. Importantly, findings from research also emphasise similarities between the roles of change managers and project managers [11]. Some scholars contend that, because of the lack of clarity about the exact working relationship between the two disciplines, not a bit of this thinking has led to the conclusion that project management in a rivalry with the set of roles referred to as change management.[12][13][14]. What follows is an experimental study aiming more about the change management arena co-opting roles for the accomplishments of project management and reporting about IT projects' outcomes.

1.1 Research problem identification

To avoid the failure of IT project has been one of the important issues among IT project managers. But what is the exact reason of this failure? And what is the solution for this? It is because IT work is continuously changing (volatile). Main change factors are organisation, technology and competitive markets. Those change factors should be retained throughout the IT project as one main success factor. Besides, change factors could help to maintain the well-quality (viable) which is one of the main success factors to avoid from failure (Product or Service is supportive to stake holders). Below is failure of IT project of Sri Lanka where lack of Change management together with project management had been one of the main factors for this failure [2][3].

Table 1. List of some IT project failures in Sri Lanka

Name	Main Reason for Failure	Findings
Lanka Government Network 2016	Poor Project Management	Rs 850.47 million was approved while Rs 148.33 million was spent on the 'Lanka Government Network' project began by the ICTA in 2016 for establishing an efficient public service by connecting government institutions through a network. The panel stated that the progress of the project was at 17 per cent.
Google Loon Project 2015	Poor Project Management	Another Initiated with the purpose of providing island-wide internet access had not been executed by the ICTA although more than Rs 1.8 million was spent to release the equipment for the project from the Customs and another Rs 6.4 million for project promotions. Project is not functioning anymore.
e-Pension project 2013	Poor Project Management	The ICTA was entrusted with the responsibility of developing the hardware and software for the project utilizing state funds to initially provide pensions to the pensioners of the Western Province via online. However, the project which was supposed to be implemented across the country has been abandoned with effect from November 01, 2013, due to 'software and hardware issues' and Rs 278.54 million has been gone to waste as a result.
e-NIPO 2016	Poor Project Management	It was disclosed that Rs 3.5 million spent on the procurement process of the e-NIPO project initiated by the National Intellectual Property Office in 2016, has been used to pay salaries of ICTA officials.
e-Local 2017	Poor Project Management	e-Local Government project which had failed was relaunched in 2016. Rs 39 million has been spent on the project as of December 31, 2017, and the COPE reprimanded the agency for not including it in the performance reports since then.

As illustrated by the examples above, if the key success factors (budget, scope and time frame) of an IT project do not adapt to the changes that occur during implementation, millions of rupees may be lost. Main objective of change management is to ensure that the project objectives and outcomes are complemented by changes, including the identification and implementation of the appropriate technologies necessary to provide value [26]. As new roles and activities begin to be implemented, change management can be a process to familiarise employees with their new tasks or further enhance their performance [27][28][30].

To prevent from failure in IT project, organizations can do suitable change management through the project management phase. Knowledge on latest tools will be an added advantage for success. Leadership monitoring, communication and team working are useful during entire phase of project management. Over the past two decades, especially after 1990, IT industry in Sri Lanka exploded but it was over engineered to meet the expectations of stakeholders. Now IT organisations are providing good products for the customer. Poor management of hassles in project management especially in changing budget, scope, technology and leadership is becoming biggest problems in the project and creates a domino effect of poor quality, poor productivity, poor reputation and poor customer satisfaction.

Information technology (IT) project management and change management are the two most prevalent management disciplines for contemporary organizations. These two management disciplines were identified as the two disciplines that have the potential to work together and contribute to the successful outcome of changes (DeLorenzo and George, 1999). The approaches to deploy change management and information technology project elements have been recognized or signified in the literature [31], however there is no consensus regarding the appropriate ways they can work together.

These two disciplines have been differentiated by how they view the relative contribution of the two disciplines in undertaking specific project activities [37]. Furthermore, the purpose of this study is to examine the impact of two management disciplines on the success criteria of a project or organization. This study also explores the ways of change management in the perception of IT project managers towards the objective of the project.

1.2 Research Questions

Q1. How does change management impact in achieving objectives in IT project management?

Q2. How do project managers see the relevance of change management to their role?

Q3. What are the recommended strategies to achieve the objectives in IT project management?

1.3 Objectives of the study

Obj1. To determine the factors of change management that affect achievement of goals in IT project management

Obj2. To Explore the perceptions of practitioners about the roles of the project management integrated with the change management in the success of IT projects

Obj3. To explore the recommending strategies in achieving IT project objectives

2. Literature review

These days, technology is necessary for every business. This technology has the management of data as well as logistics. According to the insight on companies and business, we cannot see any tech-oriented business who doesn't need software to manage their networks and purchase orders. However, even the company which is completely different from tech-oriented, there is need to use software to manage their network and purchase orders. IT project management is a process by which organizations can achieve their technology goals. This process facilitates to see that all the goals are being taken. IT project management is a process for guiding multiple tasks and activities associated with the development and implementation of information technology projects [32].

The role responsibility of an IT Project manager is to manage all the process of planning, budgeting and finish the projects on time, generating amazing projects and finishing them on time. Maintaining the projects that are finalized and finished will be a major role of an IT Project manager. To know things, 2017. Additional duties of an IT manager are to cover in getting the hardware in the IT industry like digital equipment and many more. Furthermore, Following the process of getting the hardware are software, websites and App development. Also, rollout, upgrading cloud computing, network solutions are other additional mechanisms of an IT manager's work. Business analytics and data management solutions, setting help-desk services, and other miscellaneous are IT manager's work.

The table will give you an information about the topline of the duty of an IT manager which they perform their jobs. Similar to any project, IT projects pass five distinctive stages. These are generally divided into the next categories [38][44].

Initiation – A goal for a project is determined. The project is created. It comes to an end. The final phase of the lifecycle involves planned divestment and company sale.

Planning – The surrounding ecosystem. It is essential to analyse the impact on the environment during a system’s lifecycle. The first step is the planning stage, where different tasks and resources are being mapped out. It is generally assumed that there will always be new technologies and therefore an IT project must be updated regularly. Consequently, the cycle approach is commonly used by project managers, and it is not an exception of IT project management. In general, project managers plan in phases.

Execution – This is the most essential step of the project’s development; all team members engage and complete the project goals. The deliverable is often the end of a project. This is a main goal of project, or a service or something produced.

Monitor and control-The project manager must manage the project to achieve the agreed timescale and financial requirements, as well as the quality of the project and the risk.

Closing- The closing phase of the project which is done after the completion of the work and after the handover of the project to the operations team.

Variable measured	Author	Year - Type of research	Findings
Objectives of IT Project Management	Muhammad Hashim	2013 Desk Review	Change impacts the project performance
	Andrade, Benito & Duarte, Luis & Garcia Joral, Fernando & Goy, Antonio & Henriques, Maria	2016 Qualitative	Version control tools are key to success in IT project performance
	Orhan Özçatalbaş	2020 Qualitative	Technology impacts change management in terms of IT project success
	Rajan, R., & Ganesan, R.	2018 Quantitative	Configuration management tool associates with change in IT Projects
Project Scope	Moira Alexander	2020 Qualitative	Project scope defines project, procedures, presumptions, and limits which impact project success
	Fabiola Nibyiza	2015 Mixed	When managing a project there are times when project implementers will have to make decision to change the project scope to be
	Jones, Snyder, Stackpole & Lambert	2011 Quantitative	Most significant scope change occur at the execution phase in the project life cycle
	Stuart D. Anderson, Keith Robert Molenaar, Cliff J. Schexnayder	2007 Mixed	Completing a project according to the baseline estimate is a challenge to any project and change in the project scope is sometimes unavoidable

Table 2. Literature Summary

3. Research Method

The thesis has its conceptual framework as the final product generating from the literature review the researcher obtained from journals, articles, and philosophies as well to avail the research goal of the inquiry. Additionally, the researcher shall constantly have a mission and aim all through the thesis to the end.

Fig 1. Conceptual framework (Author developed)

A critical review of literature is available particularly on the association between determined independent variables and dependent variables which emphasized in the previous chapter and based on conceptual framework, below-mentioned research hypotheses are developed by the author.

Table 3. Hypothesis (Source: The Author developed)

H1	A: Project scope has a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
	N: Project scope has no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H2	A: Budget has a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
	N: Budget has no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H3	A: Management has a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
	N: Management has no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H4	A: Quality has a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
	N: Quality has no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H5	A: Resource allocation has a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
	N: Resource allocation has no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H6	A: New technologies have a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
	N: New technologies have no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management

Operationalization table makes possible converting highly abstracted concepts depicted by the independent and dependent variable into possible indicators for measurement. (Priya Bhandari p. 2020). the table of operation is one of the most frequently used methods in the methods of the research, that provides details about the same indicators, their meaning in a pure research instrument, the origin of the author of the instrument from which some of the remarks were derived. The below table comprises the operational information of this study.

Table 4. Operationalization Table (Source: Author Developed)

Variable	Measuring Indicator	Ques No.	Measuring Scale
Independent Variables			
Project Scope	New regulations	PS1	1-5 Likert Scale
	Project performance	PS2	
	Final product	PS3	
	Project feasibility	PS4	
Budget	Decision making	B1	1-5 Likert Scale
	Proof of evidence	B2	
	Success measurement	B3	
	Financial risk	B4	
Management	Management role	M1	1-5 Likert Scale
	Leadership	M2	
	Progress review	M3	
	Job security	M4	
Quality	Project quality	Q1	1-5 Likert Scale
	Quality management	Q2	
	Quality checklist	Q3	
	Stakeholder satisfaction	Q4	
Resource Allocation	Time frame	RA1	1-5 Likert Scale
	Capacity of the team	RA2	
	Capacity measurement	RA3	
	Teamwork	RA4	
Technology	Communication	T1	1-5 Likert Scale
	Access permission	T2	
	knowledge & expertise	T3	
	Information access	T4	
Dependent Variable			
Achieving Objectives of IT Projects -	Expected result	APO1	1-5 Likert Scale
	Customer expectation	APO2	
	Quality level	APO3	
	Cost of bugs	APO4	
	Accuracy of the deliverables	APO5	

3.1 Sampling Design

The most important feature of the statistics is the sampling. In this assignment, it is taken the Stratified Random Sampling technique because the population is large in an IT industry of Sri Lanka. The stratified method is very high accuracy and this uniqueness. The population is separated to three different modules. They are Project Management; Business Analysis, Development and Quality Assurance. Anyone professional who is related to the IT industry has the same chance to get selected.

3.2 Population

Currently, over 300 enterprises and by serving over 200 industry verticals, the Information Technology Services industry is the 4th largest export-earning industry for the country. (As in March 2020, there were over 120,000 people employed in the industry, providing professional services (ICTA, 2020). It can be understood from Sekaran that “the whole universe that a researcher wanted to study described as population”. In view of the high numbers of people working in this industry, this study aims to focus on the people working in the Information Technology (IT) industry in Colombo.

3.3 Sample Selection Procedure

According to the Convenience Sampling, the data will be collected from most of IT companies are found in Colombo. All the major companies have resided this area. There would be 5 to 10 reputed IT companies in Colombo, who are still practicing the Project Management in large scale. Similarly, the sample will be selected for the purpose of the study. The employees those are more involved in Software, Networking, Security and ERP will be considered as per their job category. For example, project management, development, quality assurance and business analysis category will be selected, as an instance. The key fundamental, that considered here is the exposure towards the IT Project management by employees with less of the experience. the more will be the distinct the more accurate the data will be.

3.4 Sample Size

Sample size is the number of participants who participates in this survey and to share the view through the adopted research strategy. The sample size of the study is limited to 250 participants to gain more accurate results from experienced IT professionals in the industry. It is believed that with this kind of size, more reliable and accurate information can be generated for larger population.

Sample (n) = 250

3.5 Data Collection Method

In this research work, the scope of fundamental philosophy was used. A structured questionnaire is one of the most used instruments in this data gathering method. Section of the questionnaire consist of five questions to solicit data about the participants' demographic factors like their gender, age, IT job category, industries experienced, and highest qualification. The scale of measurement for all these dates was the nominal datum. The section two of the questionnaire comprises of 24 items. however, the section two questions were scored for an Interval scale which probes have five-point Likert scale starting, to strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5).

The survey which is distributed by virtually, the form prepared via google form and the member of group to forward to each other's via WhatsApp groups and to respondents the email address.

To avoid the incidents of missing values, google form facilitates compulsorily form response within 10 days period.

The author prefers secondary data from the primary data collection mentioned above. Books, private sources, journals, newspapers, websites, government documents, etc., which are already available, are preferred as secondary.

3.6 Statistical techniques for research analysis

The researcher analyzed the data gathered from the questionnaire using the SPSS tool, and then discussed how to interpret the findings. Considering the statistical requirements for this investigation, the following statistical analysis techniques were used.

- The establishment of validity and reliability (Checking missing values and Cronbach Alpha, KMO, Bartlett's test of sphericity)
- Testing Hypothesis
- Correlation Coefficient
- Multiple Regression Analysis

4. Results and findings

Most of the respondents are male (176) followed by females (77) have participated for the survey. In Sri Lanka, most of the IT industry workers are males.

4.1 Age

Most of the respondents are belong to the age group between 20 – 30 and 31 to 40 age group and the percentage is 72 and 25 respectively.

Fig 2. Gender (Source: Author developed)

Fig 2. Age (Source: Author developed)

4.2 IT Job Category

Specific job roles have the best experience with change management in IT projects. Here, most of the respondents are Business Analysts (35.97%) followed by Developers (35.57) and Project Management (13.83)

Fig using main data)

3. IT Job Category (Source: Generated

4.3 Education Qualification

Another important factor to consider and the highest category represents graduates (70.99 %), followed by postgraduates (25.19 %) and undergraduate (3.05%).

Fig 4. Educational Qualification (Source: Generated using main data)

4.4 Experience in the IT Industry

Especially in IT projects, experienced people can see the impact of change other than the normal staff. The sample set indicates that the most participants have 4-5 years of experience with IT projects followed by the participants with 6-8 years of industry experience.

Fig 5. Experience (Source: Generated using main data)

4.5 Independent & Dependent Variables

This study considers six independent variables towards the impact of change in IT projects. Each variable towards dependent variable in Cronbach test revealed this sample set is within the accepted validity range as below.

Table 5. Reliability Test (Source: Generated using main data)

Variable	Cronbach's alpha
Accepted Range	$\alpha \geq 0.7$
Project Scope	.719
Budget	.755
Management	.762
Quality	.836
Resource Allocation	.731
New Technologies	.710
IT Project Objectives (DV)	.719

The output result obtained for assessing the reliability of all the variables is mentioned in the below table. Cronbach's alpha value remains at .925, which has a perfect internal consistency within variables to continue further analysis.

Table 6. Reliability Statistics (Source: Generated using main data)

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.925	.925	7

If we consider the overall value of KMO & Bartlett's test, the value is 0.807 which is more significant than the recommended value of 0.5 and perfect to move forward with the analysis.

Table 7. KMO and Bartlett's Test (Source: Generated using main data)

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.807
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1632.389
	df	21
	Sig.	.000

4.6 Missing Values

The dataset can be affected with missing values. It is mandatory to test for missing values and this research does not identify any missing value as it is mandatory to fill all the questions shared via online.

PS2. Adjusting the project scope makes the project feasible. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

Fig 6: Mandatory Fields in Questionnaire (Source: Generated using main data)

4.7 Normality

Normal Q-Q plot depicts scattered plots for each variable that points fall closer to the line. It justifies that the dataset is distributed normally for each variable.

Fig 7. Normal Q-Q Plot (Source: Generated using main data)

The many correlations between the different components were evaluated using the Pearson correlation coefficient. This makes it simpler to decide whether there is a strong linear association between the variables. The coefficient's value lies between +1 and -1. A perfect positive association is represented by a level of +1, and a perfect negative association is represented by a level of -1. There is no relationship between the two things if the outcome is 0.

The relationship can be either positive or negative. This means that a correlation could be statistically significant if the significance index is smaller than the alpha (0.05) coefficient. Descriptive analysis is based on the mean and standard deviation. Mean is mean value of the values, and standard deviation is value of variation of the values relatively to the mean value.

4.8 Descriptive Analysis - Project Scope

Fig 8. Project Scope (Source: Generated using main data)

The mean is 3.4617 and the respondents believe that the changes in Project Scope have an impact towards project objectives. The Std. Deviation value is listed as .79293, and it implies that some of the respondents are not confident with the impact of Project Scope towards the association of Project Objectives but based on overall statistical analysis, it justifies that the more proportion of participants in Sri Lanka's IT industry have accepted the statements in the questionnaire, generally.

4.9 Validation of Hypothesis - Project Scope

H1A	Project scope has a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H1N	Project scope has no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management

Fig 9. Hypothesis 01 (Source: Generated using main data)

		ITProject_Obj ectives	Project_Scop e
ITProject_ Objectives	Pearson Correlation	1	.563**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	243	243
Project_Scope	Pearson Correlation	.563**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	243	243

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Fig 10. Correlation- Project Scope (Source: Generated using main data)

As depicted above, the correlation coefficient value is .563 which is significant at 0.01 level. This indicates a positive relationship between the two variables of Project Scope and IT Project Objectives. To evaluate the acceptance or the rejection, Sig value needs to be considered and it is .000 which is considered as a statistically significant correlation as it is below than the value of 0.05. In other words, change of a one variable affects to the other variable. In conclusion, Project Scope and the IT Project Objectives has a strong relationship. In this case, null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.563 ^a	.317	.314	.60894

a. Predictors: (Constant), Project_Scope

Fig 11. Model Summary- Project Scope (Source: Generated using main data)

Fig 12 Project Scope-Scatterplot Graph (Source: Generated using main data)

In the Model Summary, R value is .563 and its square root (R²) is .317. In other words, Project Scope affects to its coefficient determination by 31% while 69% covered by other variables including the remaining 05 recognize variables of this research. In scatterplot graph, the gap between points and the line is a bit high. The more the R² value is closer to 1, the dotted points go closer to the regression line.

4.10 Descriptive Analysis – Budget

Fig 13. Budget (Source: Generated using main data)

The mean is 3.4165 and the respondents believe that the changes in Budget have an impact towards achieving project objectives. The Std. Deviation value is listed as .72412, and it implies that some of the respondents are not satisfied with the impact of Budget towards the association of Project Objectives, but based on overall statistical analysis, it justifies that the more proportion of participants in Sri Lanka’s IT industry have accepted the statements in the questionnaire, generally.

4.11 Validation of Hypothesis – Budget

H2A	Budget has a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H2N	Budget has no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management

Fig 14. Hypothesis 2 (Source: Generated using main data)

		ITProject_Obj ectives	Budget
ITProject_Objectives	Pearson Correlation	1	.606**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	243	243
Budget	Pearson Correlation	.606**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	243	243

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Fig 15. Budget-Correlation (Source: Generated using main data)

The correlation coefficient value is .606 which is significant at 0.01 level. This indicates a positive strong relationship between the two variables of Budget and IT Project Objectives. Sig value needs to be considered to evaluate the hypothesis, and it is .000 which is considered as a statistically significant correlation as it is below than the value of 0.05. In other words, Budget and the IT Project Objectives has a strong relationship. In that case, getting change of a one variable affects to the change of the other variable. In conclusion, null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.606 ^a	.368	.365	.58581

a. Predictors: (Constant), Budget

Fig 16. Model Summary - Budget (Source: Generated using main data)

Figure 4.19: Budget-Scatterplot Graph (Source: Generated using main data)

In the Model Summary, R value is .606 and its square root (R²) is .368. In other words, Budget affects to its coefficient determination by 36% while the remaining 64% is covered by other variables including the remaining 05 recognize variables of this research. In scatterplot graph, the gap between points and the line is a bit high. The more the R² value is closer to 1, the dotted points go closer to the regression line.

4.12 Descriptive Analysis – Management

Fig 17. Management (Source: Generated using main data)

The mean is 3.4584 and the respondents believe that the changes in Management have an impact towards achieving project objectives. The Std. Deviation value is .73296, and it implies that some of the respondents are not confident with the impact of Management towards the association of Project Objectives, but based on overall statistical analysis, it justifies that the more proportion of participants in Sri Lanka’s IT industry have accepted the statements in the questionnaire, generally.

4.13 Validation of Hypothesis - Management

H3A	Management has a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H3N	Management has no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management

Fig 18. Hypothesis 3 (Source: Generated using main data)

		ITProject_Obj ectives	Management
ITProject_Objectives	Pearson Correlation	1	.615**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	243	243
Management	Pearson Correlation	.615**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	243	243

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Fig 19. Management- Correlation (Source: Generated using main data)

The correlation coefficient value is .615 which is significant at 0.01 level. This indicates a positive strong relationship between the two variables of Management and IT Project Objectives. Sig value needs to be considered to evaluate the

hypothesis, and it is .000 which is considered as a statistically significant correlation as it is below than the standard value of 0.05. In other words, change of a one variable affects to the change of the other variable and in conclusion, Management variable and the IT Project Objectives have a strong relationship. Therefore, alternative hypothesis is accepted, and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.615 ^a	.379	.376	.58062

a. Predictors: (Constant), Management

Fig 20. Model Summary – Management (Source: Generated using main data)

Fig 21. Management-Scatterplot Graph (Source: Generated using main data)

In the Model Summary, R value is .615 and its square root (R²) is .379. In other words, Management affects to its coefficient determination by 37% while the remaining 63% is covered by other unknown variables including the remaining 05 recognize variables of this research. In scatterplot graph, the gap between points and the line is a bit high. The more the R² value is closer to 1, the dotted points go closer to the regression line.

4.14 Descriptive Analysis – Quality

Quality		
N	Valid	243
	Missing	0
Mean		3.5753
Median		3.6000
Mode		3.40
Std. Deviation		.68975

Fig 22. Quality (Source: Generated using main data)

The mean is 3.5753 and the respondents believe that the changes in Quality have an impact towards achieving project objectives. The Std. Deviation value is .68975, and it implies that some of the participants are not confident with the impact of Quality towards the association of Project Objectives, but based on overall statistical analysis, it justifies that the more proportion of participants generally, in Sri Lanka's IT industry have accepted the statements in the questionnaire.

4.15 Validation of Hypothesis - Quality

H4A	Quality has a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H4N	Quality has no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management

Fig 23. Hypothesis 4 (Source: Generated using main data)

		ITProject_Obj ectives	Quality
ITProject_Objectives	Pearson Correlation	1	.719**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	243	243
Quality	Pearson Correlation	.719**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	243	243

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Fig 24. Quality- Correlation (Source: Generated using main data)

The correlation coefficient value is .719 which is significant at 0.01 level. This indicates a positive strong relationship between the two variables of Quality and IT Project Objectives. Meantime, Sig value needs to be considered to evaluate the hypothesis, and it is .000 which is considered as a statistically significant correlation as it is below than the standard value of 0.05. In this case, change of a one variable affects to the other variable and in conclusion, Quality variable and the IT Project Objectives have a strong relationship. Therefore, alternative hypothesis is accepted, and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.719 ^a	.517	.515	.51180

a. Predictors: (Constant), Quality

Fig 25. Model Summary -Quality (Source: Generated using main data)

Fig 26. Quality-Scatterplot Graph (Source: Generated using main data)

In the Model Summary, R value is .719 and its square root (R2) is .517. In other words, Quality affects to its coefficient determination by 51% while the remaining 49% is covered by other unknown variables and the remaining 05 recognize variables of this research. In scatterplot graph, the gap between points and the line is moderate. The more the R2 value is closer to 1, the dotted points go closer to the regression line.

4.16 Descriptive Analysis – Resource Allocation

Fig 27. Resource Allocation (Source: Generated using main data)

The mean is 3.4914 and the respondents believe that the changes in Resource Allocation have an impact towards achieving project objectives. The Std. Deviation value is .74770 and it implies that some of the participants are not satisfied with the impact of Resource Allocation towards the association of Project Objectives, but based on overall statistical analysis, it justifies that the more proportion of participants, in Sri Lanka's IT industry have accepted the statements in the questionnaire, generally.

4.17 Validation of Hypothesis – Resource Allocation

H5A	Resource allocation has a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H5N	Resource allocation has no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management

Fig 28.Hypothesis 5 (Source: Generated using main data)

		ITProject_Obj ectives	Resource_All ocation
ITProject_Objectives	Pearson Correlation	1	.577**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	243	243
Resource_Allocation	Pearson Correlation	.577**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	243	243

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Fig 29. Resource Allocation- Correlation (Source: Generated using main data)

The correlation coefficient value is .577 which is significant at 0.01 level. This indicates a positive relationship between the two variables of Resource Allocation and IT Project Objectives. Meantime, Sig value needs to be considered to evaluate the hypothesis, and it is .000 which is considered as a statistically significant correlation. In this case, change of a one variable affects to the other variable and in conclusion, resource allocation variable and the IT project objectives have a strong relationship. Therefore, alternative hypothesis is accepted, and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.577 ^a	.332	.330	.60189

a. Predictors: (Constant), Resource_Allocation

Fig 30. Model Summary- Resource Allocation (Source: Generated using main data)

Fig 31. Resource Allocation-Scatterplot Graph (Source: Generated using main data)

In the Model Summary, R value is .577 and its square root (R2) is .332. In other words, Resource Allocation affects to its coefficient determination by 33% while the remaining 67% is covered by other unknown variables and the remaining 05 recognized variables of this research. In scatterplot graph, the gap between points and the line is moderately high. The more the R2 value is closer to 1, the dotted points go closer to the regression line.

4.18 Descriptive Analysis – Technology

Technology

Technology		
N	Valid	243
	Missing	0
Mean		3.4593
Median		3.4000
Mode		3.20
Std. Deviation		.75566

Fig 32. Technology (Source: Generated using main data)

The mean is 3.4593 and the respondents believe that the changes in Technology have an impact towards achieving project objectives. The Std. Deviation value is .75566, and it implies that some of the participants are not satisfied with the impact of Technology towards the association of Project Objectives, but based on overall statistical analysis, it justifies that the more proportion of participants generally, in Sri Lanka's IT industry have accepted the statements in the questionnaire.

4.19 Validation of Hypothesis – Technology

H6A	New technologies have a relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management
H6N	New technologies have no relationship with achieving objectives in IT project management

Fig 33. Hypothesis 6 (Source: Generated using main data)

		ITProject_Obj ectives	Technology
ITProject_Objectives	Pearson Correlation	1	.550**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	243	243
Technology	Pearson Correlation	.550**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	243	243

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Fig 34. Technology- Correlation (Source: Generated using main data)

The correlation coefficient value is .550 which is significant at 0.01 level. This indicates a positive relationship between the two variables of technology and IT Project Objectives. Meantime, Sig value is .000 which is considered as a statistically significant correlation. In this case, change of a one variable affects to the other variable and in conclusion, technology and the IT project objectives have a moderate positive relationship. Therefore, alternative hypothesis is accepted, and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.550 ^a	.303	.300	.61521

a. Predictors: (Constant), Technology

Fig 35. Model Summary -Technology (Source: Generated using main data)

Fig 36. Technology-Scatterplot Graph (Source: Generated using main data)

In the Model Summary, R value is .550 and its square root (R2) is .303. In other words, Technology affects to its coefficient determination by 30% while the remaining 70% is covered by other unknown variables and the remaining 05 recognized variables of this research. In scatterplot graph, the gap between points and the line is moderately high. The more the R2 value is closer to 1, the dotted points go closer to the regression line.

4.20 Descriptive Analysis – IT Project Objectives (IV)

ITProject_Objectives		
N	Valid	243
	Missing	0
Mean		3.5350
Median		3.4000
Mode		3.20
Std. Deviation		.73511

Fig 37. IT Project Objectives (Source: Generated using main data)

The mean is 3.5350 and the respondents believe that the Achieving Project Objectives is an important factor in IT industry. The Std. Deviation value is .73511 and it implies that some of the participants are not satisfied with Project Objectives, but based on overall statistical analysis, it justifies that the more proportion of participants, in Sri Lanka's IT industry have accepted the statements in the questionnaire, generally.

4.21 Multiple Regression for Model Testing

As cited in the conceptual framework of the research, the author continued analysis towards model testing, and testing hypotheses will finalize its accordance.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.782 ^a	.612	.602	.46350

a. Predictors: (Constant), Technology, Budget, Quality, Resource_Allocation, Management, Project_Scope

Fig 38. Model Summary- All Variables (Source: Generated using main data)

The over-role strength of the association between independent and dependent variables is indicated by the R2 which is .612 and the Adjusted R Square value is .602. In other words, independent variables in this research contribute 61% to the Impact of IT Project Objectives and only 39% is remained unknown.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	80.072	6	13.345	62.119	.000 ^b
	Residual	50.701	236	.215		
	Total	130.773	242			

a. Dependent Variable: ITProject_Objectives

b. Predictors: (Constant), Technology, Budget, Quality, Resource_Allocation, Management, Project_Scope

Fig 39. Anova Table (Source: Generated using main data)

In the ANOVA table, the most significant factor is "F" and "Sig" values which interpret whether the group of independent variables, when used together, can predict the accuracy of dependent variable. According to the table above, F is 62.119 which is high, and Sig is .000 which is below 0.05 notifies that the model is acceptable.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.145	.181		.799	.425
	Project_Scope	-.267	.110	-.288	-2.435	.016
	Budget	.367	.086	.362	4.285	.000
	Management	.302	.110	.301	2.745	.007
	Quality	.422	.063	.396	6.714	.000
	Resource_Allocation	.140	.087	.142	1.608	.109
	Technology	.006	.094	.006	.063	.950

a. Dependent Variable: ITProject_Objectives

Figure 4.43: Coefficients Table (Source: Generated using main data)

Coefficient table represents an analysis in relation to the “sig” value. The standard recommendation is, if the alpha is below 0.05, it would be statistically significant that there is strong relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. Based on this, in the model result, sig values for independent variables are .016, .000, .007, .000, .109 and .950 respectively. As the technology has a value of greater than 0.05, it depicts that the technology has a low relationship with the model, but all the other variables have strong relationship with the model.

4.22 4.5. Summary of Data Analysis

Table 6. Summary of Hypotheses (Source: Generated using main data)

No	Hypotheses	Correlation Sig Value (p)	Accepted/Rejected.
H1	Change of project scope during the project impacts achieving objectives of the IT project	.000	Accepted
H2	Change of budget during the project impacts achieving objectives of the IT project	.000	Accepted
H3	Change of project manager during the project impacts achieving objectives of the IT project	.000	Accepted
H4	Change in quality during the project impacts the achieving objectives of the IT project	.000	Accepted
H5	Change of Resource allocation during the project impacts achieving objectives of the IT project	.000	Accepted
H6	New technology adopted during the project impacts achieving objectives of the IT project.	.000	Accepted

Based on Pearson Correlation Coefficient the all the hypothesis are accepted, making the conceptual model developed by the author, a successful one. With adjusted r² value, it's contribution to the existing literature is also huge and overall, the research is successful based on the data analysis part.

5. Conclusion

As mentioned in literature review, so many determinants are there which affect in achieving objectives in IT project management. After analysing existing literature, a conceptual model is developed by the researcher which includes Scope, Budget, Management, Quality, Resource Allocation and Technology, followed by the hypotheses tested using 243 responses from well reputed IT companies in Sri Lanka.

All the responses have analysed using SPSS and proved that there is a strong positive relationship among them with achieving objectives in IT project management by accepting the alternative hypothesis and reject all the null hypotheses. Meantime, the contribution of independent variables is overall 61% to the IT project objectives and it seems

most of the areas are covered via those variables. In conclusion, all the change management factors Scope, Budget, Management, Quality, Resource Allocation and Technology can be identified as the factors that affects in IT project objectives. Survey questions are designed mostly from the viewpoint of project management. In other words, the way the project managers might see the change in relation to the Scope, Budget, Management, Quality, Resource Allocation and Technology. All the responses have a positive strong relationship with the dependent variable of IT project objectives and mean value is also closer to the strongly agree position in the Likert scale. All the respondents are restricted to IT job categories of Project Management, Business Analysis, Developers and Quality Assurance to get the best view from the responses as those IT professionals have the best experience with the role of a project manager. With this one the objective of exploring the view on practitioners on the role of project management is fulfilled.

As a recommendation to the modern-day tec companies, when we gather requirement from the stakeholders, involvement of senior level business analysts and technical leads should be mandatory. So, the requirement can be assessed from two different angles, one is from the business point of view, other from the technical point of view. When defining the scope change, its impact towards the existing product and limitation must be documented. From this kind of process, human made mistakes can be prevented and in Sri Lanka the issue is there is no proper documentation and most of the changes are verbally handled. This process is something that needs to be implemented by the Project Management team. The more the process gets smooth, the more the reliability is.

Budget of the project is crucial. Even managers do mistakes by not calculating the budget properly. As an instance, costs of labour, material, transportation, research, technical resources, external consultants, and trainings must be included to the budget to calculate the cost. As a best practice, checklists can be maintained within the company. So, moving forward, new cost types can also be added to the project budget. It is not suitable to rely on senior project management for each task. As a company, it should move forward even with management changes. As a solution, new technology can be used for budgeting. Now in the market there are budgeting tools that create budgets more easily and budget tracker tools that track the progress of the budget of an ongoing project can also be used with a lower cost. With the establishment of proper budget planning tools within the company, it will help in decision making and forecasting more accurately.

Management gets change and it is a common symptom. As a recommendation, use of technical tools in project management can reduce the risk from 75%. There are some tools like Azure DevOps that created especially for the purpose giving more insight to the project management. Budget, scope changes and all the other documents can be included here, and it can track the progress and decision making will be a lot easier with figures. Even with change of a manager, the new manager can start working in the existing project without an issue. Meantime, when selecting candidates for the managerial level positions, it is important to follow a strict interview process, especially when it comes IT projects as the previous experience matters. To improve the quality, test automation can be taken as a step. With manual testing it will be time consuming. Most importantly, a test automation targeted basic validation will be a good solution in software development. Therefore, the developers can run it in the initial stages of the development to recognize bugs. According to scholars, the cost of bugs can be eliminated by 50% if it recognizes in the early stages. From the management perspective, allocate extra time for quality assurance is a must specially in an IT project. To improve the resource allocation process, the global trend is to use tools that built considering IT trends. In Sri Lanka, such tools are not famous, sometimes the companies are not willing to go for a change. This is because of resistance to change. As an instance, Azure DevOps can be taken. Here, the project and estimation of the task is determined and then the resources can be allocated based on their working hours, performance and even reallocation to other works can be monitored. This prevent resources are being idle and helps to get the maximum within them. Sometimes, the project manager needs to figure out the strength of the resources.

IT technologies are getting changed every time. Recommendation is to stay up to date with moving technologies. Therefore, it is necessary to make arrangement to train with bootcamps, international webinars, technical sessions and following certification processes. Giving resource the time, resources to train and funds for certification is a responsibility of the management of a company. With such an involvement, the organization can take the benefits in the long-term run.

Objectives of the research, which were mentioned in background are successfully achieved and all the results have showed that the variables identified in this research have a strong positive relationship with the dependent variable to prove that the selection of variables are correct, and all the alternative hypotheses are accepted in relation to Pearson Correlation. During the data analysis part, it is identified that all the tests are within the accepted range

Recommendation for improvements is depicted based on the responses of questionnaire where the participants have different kind of opinions. Meantime, the sample is with high accuracy and reliability, and selected sample believed to be the cream that represents the IT industry in Sri Lanka. When it comes to IT industry, traditional methods are following to handle the issues without tools, documentation, and best practices. Sometimes, spending cash on technical tools are prohibited due to conventional thinking pattern. Sometimes, it is all about the risk, the more the organization takes the risk, the more profit they earn but willingness to go for that opportunity is low. Overall, with all the results obtained, makes this research a successful and its contribution to the existing literature and future studies are massive.

References

- [1] M. Campbell-Kelly, *From Mainframes to Smartphones*. 2015. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4159/9780674286535>
- [2] ICTA, “Sri Lanka ICT workforce to grow 16.0-pct in 2019: survey,” *EconomyNext*, Aug. 07, 2019. Available: <https://economynext.com/sri-lanka-ict-workforce-to-grow-16-0-pct-in-2019-survey-15026>. [Accessed: May 31, 2024]
- [3] ICTA, “ICT industry in Sri Lanka expected to generate USD 1.8 billion revenue by 2022: JLL- ICTA Report | ශ්‍රී ලංකා තොරතුරු හා සන්නිවේදන තාක්ෂණ නියෝජිතායතනය - ICTA,” *ICTA*, Nov. 16, 2021. Available: <https://www.icta.lk/news/ict-industry-in-sri-lanka-expected-to-generate-usd-1-8-billion-revenue-by-2022-jll-icta-report/>
- [4] G. W. Coffey, *A systems approach to leadership : how to create sustained high performance in a complex and uncertain environment*. Berlin ; London: Springer, 2010.
- [5] J. Pollack and C. Algeo, “Perspectives on the Formal Authority between Project Managers and Change Managers,” *Project Management Journal*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 27–43, Oct. 2014, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pmj.21446>
- [6] A. Orb, L. Eisenhauer, and D. Wynaden, “Ethics in Qualitative Research,” *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 93–96, Mar. 2001, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1547-5069.2001.00093.x>
- [7] Dr. Mukul Burghate I Dr. Ninad Gawande, *Organisational Behaviour (OB)*. mukul burghate.
- [8] P. Bingi, M. K. Sharma, and J. K. Godla, “Critical Issues Affecting an ERP Implementation,” *Information Systems Management*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 7–14, Jun. 1999, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1201/1078/43197.16.3.19990601/31310.2>. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1201/1078/43197.16.3.19990601/31310.2>
- [9] A. Liberati *et al.*, “The PRISMA Statement for Reporting Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses of Studies That Evaluate Health Care Interventions: Explanation and Elaboration,” *PLoS Medicine*, vol. 6, no. 7, p. e1000100, Jul. 2009, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000100>. Available: <https://journals.plos.org/plosmedicine/article?id=10.1371/journal.pmed.1000100>
- [10] A. Ghanim, “Project and Change Management Success Factors from Malaysian Government Departments and Agencies Perspective,” *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 36–45, 2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.9790/487x-1123645>
- [11] H. Krchova and K. Svejnova Hoesova, “The impact of modern communication marketing tools to increase the innovativeness of business,” *Marketing and Management of Innovations*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 117–126, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.21272/mmi.2021.3-10>

- [12] P. A. Wickham and L. Wickham, *Management consulting : delivering an effective project*. Harlow, England ; New York: Financial Times/Prentice Hall, 2008.
- [13] É. Alsène, “Internal changes and project management structures within enterprises,” *International Journal of Project Management*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 367–376, Dec. 1999, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0263-7863\(98\)00057-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0263-7863(98)00057-x)
- [14] T. Althiyabi and R. Qureshi, “Predefined Project Scope Changes and its Causes for Project Success,” *International Journal of Software Engineering & Applications*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 45–56, May 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.5121/ijsea.2021.12304>. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351946150_Predefined_Project_Scope_Changes_and_its_Causes_for_Project_Success
- [15] R. Azevedo, “What is the cost of a bug?,” *Rafaela Azevedo*, Apr. 27, 2018. Available: <https://azevedorafaela.com/2018/04/27/what-is-the-cost-of-a-bug/>
- [16] Boon Siong Neo, Kwong Sin Leong, and Nanyang Technological University. Information Management Research Centre, *Managing Risks in Information Technology Projects*. 1991.
- [17] J. F. Wilson and A. Thomson, “Management in Historical Perspective: Stages and Paradigms,” *Competition & Change*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 357–374, Dec. 2006, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1179/102452906x160996>
- [18] M. B. Tengli, “Research Onion: A Systematic Approach to Designing Research Methodology | | Welcome to AESA,” *Aesa*, Aug. 27, 2020. Available: <https://www.aesanetwork.org/research-onion-a-systematic-approach-to-designing-research-methodology/>
- [19] C. Scott, *The Project in International Development*. Taylor & Francis, 2023.
- [20] G. L. De, *Project management recipes for success*. Boca Raton: Auerbach, 2017.
- [21] Attila Dikbas and R. Scherer, *eWork and eBusiness in Architecture, Engineering and Construction*. Taylor & Francis, 2004.
- [22] O. V. Dubinina and L. D. Hrytsiak, “USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN FUTURE PROJECT MANAGERS’ TRAINING,” *Information Technologies and Learning Tools*, vol. 63, no. 1, p. 107, Feb. 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.33407/itlt.v63i1.2038>
- [23] K. E. Emam and A. G. Koru, “A Replicated Survey of IT Software Project Failures,” *IEEE Software*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 84–90, Sep. 2008, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ms.2008.107>. Available: https://ruor.uottawa.ca/bitstream/10393/12988/1/EI_Emam_Khaled_2008_A_replicated_survey_of_IT_software.pdf
- [24] A. Errida and B. Lotfi, “The Determinants of Organizational Change Management Success: Literature Review and Case Study,” *International Journal of Engineering Business Management*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2021.
- [25] O. Eyibo and C. O. Daniel, “The Effective Resource Budgeting as a Tool for Project Management,” *Asian Journal of Business and Management*, vol. 8, no. 2, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.24203/ajbm.v8i2.6190>. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342597352_The_Effective_Resource_Budgeting_as_a_Tool_for_Project_Management
- [26] B. J. Galli, “Change management models: A comparative analysis and concerns,” *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 124–132, Sep. 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMR.2018.2866860>. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8486843>
- [27] L. Crawford, A. Aitken, and Anat Hassner-Nahmias, *Project management and organizational change*. Newtown Square, Pennsylvania: Project Management Institute, 2014.
- [28] C. Kaufmann and A. Kock, “Does project management matter? The relationship between project management effort, complexity, and profitability,” *International Journal of Project Management*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 624–633, Jul. 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2022.05.007>. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S026378632200076X>

- [29] H. Kerzner, *PROJECT MANAGEMENT : a systems approach to planning, scheduling, and controlling.*, 12th ed. S.L.: John Wiley & Sons, 2017.
- [30] P. Lech, “Time, Budget, And Functionality?—IT Project Success Criteria Revised,” *Information Systems Management*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 263–275, Jul. 2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10580530.2013.794658>
- [31] V. Lehmann, “Connecting changes to projects using a historical perspective: Towards some new canvases for researchers,” *International Journal of Project Management*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 328–338, May 2010, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2010.01.011>
- [32] J. M. Nicholas and H. Steyn, *Project Management for Engineering, Business and Technology*. Routledge, 2017.
- [33] ProjectManager, “Project Management Software - ProjectManager.com,” *ProjectManager.com*, 2019. Available: <https://www.projectmanager.com/>
- [34] G. Alleman, *Performance-Based Project Management*. AMACOM, 2014.
- [35] A. Mento, R. Jones, and W. Dirndorfer, “A change management process: Grounded in both theory and practice,” *Journal of Change Management*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 45–59, Mar. 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/714042520>
- [36] M. Martinsuo and P. Hoverfält, “Change program management: Toward a capability for managing value-oriented, integrated multi-project change in its context,” *International Journal of Project Management*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 134–146, Jan. 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2017.04.018>
- [37] K. Ganesh, Sanjay Mohapatra, S. P. Anbudayasankar, and P. Sivakumar, *Enterprise Resource Planning : Fundamentals of Design and Implementation*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2014.
- [38] Project Management Institute, *A guide to the project management body of knowledge*, 6th ed. Newtown Square, Pennsylvania, USA: Project Management Institute, 2017.
- [39] A. R. Peslak, “Information Technology Project Management and Project Success,” *International Journal of Information Technology Project Management*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 31–44, Jul. 2012, doi: <https://doi.org/10.4018/jitpm.2012070103>
- [40] S. Berzisa and J. Grabis, “Project Phase Dependent Configuration of Project Management Information Systems,” *Information Technology and Management Science*, vol. 15, no. 1, Jan. 2012, doi: <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10313-012-0011-x>
- [41] “Software project management,” *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 29, no. 8, p. 458, Oct. 1987, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0950-5849\(87\)90302-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0950-5849(87)90302-8)
- [42] P. Serrador and R. Turner, “The Relationship between Project Success and Project Efficiency,” *Project Management Journal*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 30–39, Feb. 2015.
- [43] G. M. Hill, *The Complete Project Management Office Handbook, Third Edition*. Auerbach Publications, 2013.
- [44] Axelos, *Managing Successful Projects with PRINCE2*, 6th ed. London: Tso, 2017.
- [45] Agile, *3rd AGILE Conference on Geographic Information Science, Helsinki/Espoo May 25-27 2000*. Helsinki/Espoo, 2000.